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ECOWAS Trade Liberalization Scheme and Economic Growth in Anglophone West Africa Countries

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme on economic growth in the five Anglophone West African countries between 1981 and 2021. The study used GDP growth rate as the dependent variable to proxy economic growth and used the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme as the main independent variable, whereas total intra exports (XPOT), total intra imports (MPOT), and exchange rate (EXRC) were used as check variables. Descriptive statistics, correlation matrix, panel unit root test, Hausman test for MG and PMG, as well as pooled mean group (PMG) modeling techniques were used for the analysis. The study shows that, in the long run across all specifications, the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme (ETLS) has a negative and insignificant relationship with economic growth, while it has a positive and an insignificant relationship in the short run. In the Gambia, ETLS has a positive and insignificant relationship with economic growth. ETLS has a negative and insignificant relationship with economic growth in Ghana. ETLS has a negative and an insignificant relationship with economic growth in Liberia; ETLS has a positive and a significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria; and ETLS has a positive and an insignificant relationship with economic growth in Sierra Leone. The study, therefore, concludes that the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme has not improved economic growth in Anglophone West African countries within the period under study. It is therefore recommended that ECOWAS member countries should fully implement the removal of tariff and non-tariff barriers in accordance with ETLS regulations and adopt a common currency within the region.

Keywords: ECOWAS Trade Liberalization Scheme, Economic Growth, Intra-Trade, Anglophone, West African Countries.

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Introduction

Trade liberalization policy is one of the factors that influence economic growth and development in an economy. This is due to the fact that trade liberalization policy is a critical enabler of growth, job creation, and poverty alleviation. Trade liberalization policy creates additional market opportunities for indigenous enterprises, higher productivity, and competition-driven innovation. It helps with poverty reduction, higher earnings, geopolitical benefits from closer economic integration, and even promotes individual choice and freedom on a personal level (Jackson, 2015).

In accordance with the foregoing, the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) launched the ECOWAS Trade Liberalization Scheme (ETLS) in 1979. The system initially only permitted agricultural, handicraft, and crude products. However, in 1990, the ETLS product list was broadened to include industrial products. Hence, the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme (ETLS) is a trade mechanism designed to promote duty-free commerce among ECOWAS member countries. The ETLS aims to liberalize trade by eliminating customs tariffs on imports and exports, as well as non-tariff obstacles among member countries in order to establish a free trade zone at the community level.

According to Akims (2014) and Unachukwu (2022), the dynamic effect of the ECOWAS Trade Liberalization Scheme (ETLS) on economic growth in West African countries is that the ETLS implies easing or removing trade barriers within the sub-region, and such freer trade will gravitate towards higher wages in general; and that when more of the country's goods are sought after, prices will rise as a result of rising demand and wages will be able to rise as a result of the price increase. They went on to say that trade liberalization policy will not only raise wages, but that a greater number of people will be working in the more productive sectors of the economy. This is due to the rising need for technology, which may be talent-biased and it will increase the demand for skilled labor, thereby reducing the army of unemployed graduates.

It is expected (both in theory and practice) that, after the implementation of the ETLS policy, the economies of the ECOWAS countries should perform better. But, a cursory look at the economies of these countries shows that perennial

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underdevelopment, poverty, increased debt burden, systematic collapse of infrastructures, unemployment, high rate of corruption, etc. are still prevalent. Nwezeaku (2010) and Ogbonna (2012) maintained that the economies of these countries are really faced with unfavourable economic indices as evidenced by a high rate of perennial and persistent inflation, fluctuating and deficit balances of payment position, low per capita income, poor income distribution, and sustained impoverishment.

Nirav (2018) says that when compared to East Asia and the Pacific's contribution to declining global poverty, and more recently, South Asia's, sub-Saharan Africa's much slower fight against poverty has been unable to match the progress of these other regions. According to the report, the number of people living in poverty in the region grew from 278 million in 1990 to 413 million in 2020. As of 2020, most of the global poor live in sub-Saharan Africa. Also, the World Bank (2020) reported that Africa is lagging behind the rest of the world.

Ajayi (2005) and Shuaibu (2015) point out that the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme has been marked by the unwillingness of many countries to implement its provisions relating to the elimination of tariff and non-tariff barriers to trade and the functioning of a compensation mechanism. Fajana (2018) as cited in Unachukwu (2022), also assert that there are numerous challenges and constraints in the implementation of the ETLS which have limited its effectiveness and impact as a tool of market integration in West Africa. These challenges include the lack of political will on the part of member states to surrender part of their sovereignty to implement the ETLS as evident from the poor domestication of the agreements and decisions and the great disconnect between adoption of policies at the regional level and implementation at the national level; inadequacy of the awareness and sensitization of the ETLS in member states; lack of trust on the part of some member states in the transparency of the process of determining product eligibility and issuing of certificate of origin under the ETLS; underdevelopment of direct taxation resulting in the heavy dependence of member states on import duties for government revenue and their reluctance to forgo such duties on imports from other member states; prevalence of non-tariff barriers that hinder the

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entry of products in spite of their duty-free status; lack of complementarity and structural transformation in the economies of member states coupled with the inadequacy of productive capacity and trade-related infrastructure and trade information; absence of an effective mechanism for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of the ETLS and of a legal framework for settlement of disputes and enforcement of rights and obligations; and capacity deficiencies (both institutional and technical) of the ECOWAS Commission.

Despite the challenges and constraints highlighted above, Ajakaiye and Ncube (2010) have observed that intra-ECOWAS trade has increased marginally within the ECOWAS sub-region as indicated by the trend in intra-ECOWAS trade as a percentage of total trade. However, scholars such as Babatunde (2006), Osabuohien (2007), Nirodha, Jaime, and Jeff (2013), Mohammed (2015), Shuaibu (2015), John and Bright (2016), Ofei (2016), Sani and Yunusa (2019), Shobande (2019), and more, have found that trade liberalization has a positive impact on the growth of the entire economy. On the contrary, Adam (2012) has it that intra-ECOWAS trade flows have remained low despite significant deployment of policy prescriptions towards a common monetary and economic union. Also, scholars like Ghani (2009), Olayiwola, Osabuohien, and Okodua (2011), Olowe and Ibraheem (2015), Asante (2018), Tyopev (2019), Duru, Okafor, Adikwu, and Njoku (2020), and more, have found trade liberalization to have negatively affected the growth of an economy and the entire economy.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Review of Theoretical Literature

2.1.1 Absolute Advantage Trade Theory

The absolute advantage trade theory was propounded by Adam Smith in his famous book, *The Wealth of Nations* published in 1776. The theory emerges as a result of the criticism levied against mercantilism. He advocated free trade as the best policy for the nations of the world. Smith argued that with free trade, each nation could specialize in the production of those commodities in which it could produce more efficiently than the other nations and import those commodities in which it could produce less efficiently.

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This international specialization of factors in production would result in an increase in world output, which would be shared by the trading nations. Thus, a nation need not gain at the expense of other nations; all nations could gain simultaneously. In other words, according to the theory, a nation should specialize in the production of export commodities in which it has lower costs or absolute cost advantages over others. On the other hand, the same country should import a commodity in which it has a higher cost or an absolute cost disadvantage (Akeem, 2011; Enu, Havi, & Hogan, 2013). By implication, this theory supports the act of buying and selling at the international level. This is because the specialization in the production of goods for which a country has a real opportunity cost advantage over others will suggest that the balance of trade is usually favorable when countries adopt the principle of absolute cost theory. This relationship justifies the inclusion of this theory in this study.

2.1.2 Comparative Advantage Theory

The theory of absolute advantage fails to analyze where a country has comparative advantage in the production of two goods as it generates this question: will trade still be necessary or beneficial to the country in question? David Ricardo tackled this question. Ricardo was the first to demonstrate that external trade arises not from differences in absolute advantage but from differences in comparative advantage. "Comparative advantage" is meant by "greater advantage". Thus, in the context of two countries and two commodities, trade would still take place even if one country was more efficient in the production of both commodities provided the degree of its superiority over the other country was not identical for both commodities.

Ricardo assumed the existence of two countries, two commodities, and one factor of production, and labor. He assumed that labor was fully employed and internationally immobile; and that the product and its factor of price were perfectly competitive. There are no transport costs or any other impediments to trade. In the context of a model of two countries, two commodities, and one factor of production, Ricardo advanced that a country will tend to export the commodity in which it has a comparative disadvantage. Since comparative costs are the other side of comparative advantage, the theory could be expressed in terms of comparative costs. Specifically, the theory now states that a country will tend to export the commodity whose comparative cost is lower in production and higher in pre-trade isolation. By implication, if this

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principle is upheld, the export (supply side) will outweigh the import (demand side) of external trade, and the balance of trade of such a country will be favorable comparatively.

The theory also assumed the level of technology to be fixed for both nations. Different nations may use different technology, but all firms within each nation utilize a common production method for each commodity. It is also assumed that trade is balanced and facilitates the flow of money between nations. The distribution of income within a nation is not affected by trade.

Most assumptions of the Ricardian theory are unrealistic. The theory is based on the labor theory of values, which states that the price of the value of a commodity is equal to or can be inferred from the quality of labor time going into its production process. The labor theory of values is based on the fact that labor is the sole factor of production. Labor is used in the same fixed proportion in the production of all commodities. Labor is homogenous. This underlying proposition is quite unrealistic because, as labor is categorized into skilled, semi-skilled, and unskilled labor, there are other factors of production.

Despite its shortcomings, the law of comparative advantage cannot be discarded because it found application in study of economics. The law is valid and can be explained in terms of opportunity cost in the modern theory of trade (Akeem, 2011; Enu, Havi, & Hogan, 2013).

2.1.3 Grossman-Helpman's Model of Growth-Cum-Trade

Grossman-Helpman's Model of Growth—Cum Trade is a new endogenous theory. The model was developed by Grossman and Helpman (1991). The theory extended the constant return to capital, or AK growth model of Paul Romer (1986 and 1989) and Robert Lucas (1988) to include trade.

The theory states that both technology and foreign trade engagement in an endogenous manner can enhance long-run growth in an economy.

According to Sena and Fontenele (2012), the main purpose of this model is to introduce some of the ways that world trade might influence the incentives for industrial innovation and growth. Innovation comes from two different sources. In one version,

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entrepreneurs develop new varieties of differentiated intermediate goods. On the other hand, entrepreneurs seek quality improvements in a given set of non-tradable factors. This amounts to specifying formulations for endogenous product variety and quality. The formal analysis of these specifications is used to establish the production side of the small, open country.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Nyairo et al. (2010) investigated the impacts of agricultural trade on market liberalization and food security in developing countries using Kenya and Zambia. Evidence from results and other literature on maize productivity in the Sub-Saharan African region indicates that the use of fertilizer significantly increases agricultural productivity. In effect, policymakers need to design national programs, extending support to maize producers in order to enable them maintain a level of production that at least meets their basic consumption needs. Maize is produced by rural farmers with limited incomes or sometimes poor production techniques. Conclusions from the research suggest that agricultural reforms led to mixed results. This may be attributed to the sometimes stop-and-go nature of reform implementation. The mixed results are reflected in the weak maize output response to price changes. Overall country economic conditions and the state of agricultural development can be attributed to the pace of response, hence, the effect on agricultural supply. Elasticity of maize output to changes in price and acreage is strongly significant in maize output for the case of Kenya. Both restricted models of maize production suggest that prior to the introduction of reforms to acreage, prices and alternative crops were more elastic when simulated with Zambian data than with Kenyan data.

Mohammad et al. (2012) examined the impact of trade liberalization and financial development on economic growth in Iran from 1966 to 2010. The study employed cointegration and principal component analysis to analyze the data. The study found that financial and trade liberalization could not influence economic growth through this channel as expected. It further revealed that the joint impact of trade liberalization and financial development in terms of economic liberalization is also positive on growth, while human and physical capital have had significant impacts.

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Yusuf et al. (2013) examined the causal relationships between trade liberalization, growth of the Nigerian economy, and poverty. It employed the recently introduced Pesaran et al. (2001) ARDL approach. Evidence from the study suggests that trade liberalization does not cause poverty reduction, implying that the benefit of trade liberalization does not trickle down to the poor in Nigeria. This suggests that countries with a high propensity to import poor commodity prices need not strictly follow the one size-fits-all trade liberalization policies, but rather, each country needs to focus on trade policies peculiar to its own environment, which can deliver growth and translate it into meaningful poverty reduction.

Akims (2014) examined Nigeria's participation in the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme and the potential gains that the country may accrue by opening up to trade in the West African sub-region. The ECOWAS Free Trade Area is to give rise to the elimination of customs duties and be accompanied by the total elimination of all non-tariff barriers and other administrative measures impeding the free flow of trade in the sub-region. Employing a deductive approach, the study posits that Nigeria stands a chance of benefiting from gains such as improved wages and employment, increased productivity in the manufacturing industry, and enhanced technological progress and economic growth. With Nigeria remaining committed to the implementation of the common external tariff, she heads toward jointly taking advantage of the opportunities of trade liberalization.

Shuaibu (2015) examined the relationship between trade liberalization and intra-regional trade in some selected ECOWAS member countries, with particular focus on the role of applied and most-favored nation import tariffs. The data utilized for the study were sourced from the World Bank's World Development and Governance Indicators, Mayer and Zignago's (2006) distance index, and the World Trade Organization's World Integrated Trade System (WITS). The sample period consists of 8 countries covering the years 1998 to 2011. Based on a gravity framework, system, and generalized method of moments, dynamic panel data estimators were relied upon. The empirical results showed that trade liberalization has contributed to intra-regional trade in the West African sub-region. The potency of trade liberalization was relatively more

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pronounced through the use of most-favorable-nation import tariffs compared to the rates applied to import tariffs. The results also showed that improved institutional quality and infrastructure are associated with higher intra-ECOWAS trade. Furthermore, using alternative measures of institutional quality and infrastructure, as well as fixed and random effect estimators validated our findings.

John and Bright (2016) explored the relationship between trade liberalization and economic growth in Nigeria from 1980 to 2013. Two equations were estimated in which the index of industrial production was proxied as yearly average capacity utilization and as function of degree of openness, terms of trade, and real export. Similarly, in the second equation, real gross domestic product as a function of degree of openness, terms of trade, and a real export and trade liberalization dummy were estimated. The study employed a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), and the results show that openness of the foreign sector and trade liberalization had a significant positive impact on both industrial performance and economic growth in Nigeria within the reviewed period.

Ofei (2016) investigated the impact of EU trade liberalization on the export competitiveness of ECOWAS countries. Trade liberalization is captured by import tariffs in the EU market, while export competitiveness is captured by the export value of ECOWAS countries. The study uses the gravity model with fixed and random effects as well as the Hausman test for country pair panel data of 15 ECOWAS and 15 EU countries for the period between 1995 and 2014. The study found a positive impact of trade liberalization on export competitiveness and estimated the export value of ECOWAS countries to increase by 0.487% for every 1% reduction of import tariffs in the EU.

Siyakiya (2017) investigated the impact of trade openness on national productivity in selected African countries over the period 1980 – 2014. In order to test whether trade openness affects different sectors differently, disaggregated data was used. Applying a pooled ordinary least squares technique and STATA software version 13, the results point to an overall positive impact of trade openness on manufacturing and service value added. When it comes to other variables, the study finds that capital

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also contributes positively to both overall and sectoral value added, while labor productivity is negative for all except service value added. The negative relationship between labor and output can be explained by decreasing returns to scale and poor managerial services. Most developing countries are capital constrained; hence, they end up using a lot of labor to the point of causing diminishing marginal productivity of labor. Based on these results, the research revealed that greater trade openness can stimulate output in developing countries. In view of the above, it is, therefore, recommended that African countries implement progressive and sectoral trade liberalization.

Tyopev (2019) examined the relationship between trade openness and economic growth in selected West African countries (Cote d'Ivoire, Ghana, and Nigeria) using a multivariate panel framework between 1970 and 2016. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bound tests, VAR Granger causality/block exogeneity Wald tests, Impulse Response Functions (IRFs) and Fixed Error Variance Decomposition (FEVD); Dumitrescu and Hurlin (2012) panel Granger causality test, as well as the fixed effect Least Squares Dummy Variable (LSDV), and other diagnostic tests were employed for data estimation. The results indicated a long-run relationship between trade openness and economic growth in Cote d'Ivoire, Ghana, and Nigeria, and that this relationship is negative and insignificant for Nigeria and Cote d'Ivoire but positive and significant for Ghana. In the short-run, changes in RGDP are driven mostly by the error correction term and short-run trade openness shocks for each country. Short-run deviations from the long-run equilibrium take 1.291 years (Cote d'Ivoire), 2.189 years (Ghana), and as long as 7.498 years (Nigeria) to return to equilibrium. The results also indicated heterogeneous non-causality (HENC), implying that causation between trade openness and economic growth exists in a subgroup of the panel. The combination of other macroeconomic variables like investment, human capital, the net inflow of FDI, and the exchange rate complements the contribution of trade to economic growth. Therefore, these countries should promote appropriate trade policies devoted to fostering increased local production of manufactured and agricultural goods to reduce importation and stimulate exports as a strategy to boost economic growth.

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Iloh et al. (2019) explored the link between the WTO's trade liberalization policy on agriculture and food security in West Africa. Specifically, they investigated whether the policy undermines food security in the sub-region by examining its impacts on food importation and food dumping. The study relied mainly on documentary evidence. Data were scooped from documents and annual publications of the WTO, UNCTAD, FAO, ECOWAS, and World Bank. Data were analyzed using content analysis rooted in logical deductions. The results of the data analysis showed that the increased dependency on international trade (as championed by the WTO) by many countries in West Africa has a number of direct and indirect implications on the realization of food security in the sub-region. Importation does not only expose producers and consumers to increased vulnerability, both to worsening terms of trade and fluctuations in commodity prices, but also exposes the domestic food-producing industries to the danger of extinction through steep competition. The study also found that relying on international trade for food supply encourages the dumping of excess products on developing countries at relatively lower prices. This harms domestic production and reduces the income of domestic farmers and other investors in the food production chain.

Mizan (2019) examined the effects of trade openness on the growth of the economies of 15 developing countries from South Asia, South East Asia, and Africa. To conduct the panel data analysis, 20 years was considered, from 1998 to 2017. The trade openness index, FDI, unemployment, official exchange rate, and population were considered as explanatory variables for the study. The fixed effects model results suggested that trade openness has no effects on economic growth. However, individual trade zone regression results suggested three different results. So, empirical evidence found that trade openness might have different effects based on the individual country's geographic location and other policies. Moreover, the Granger Causality Test was employed to check the cause-and-effect relation between exports, imports, and economic growth. The study concluded there is a unidirectional relationship from exports to GDP and from GDP to imports.

Sheikh et al. (2020) empirically examined the implications of trade openness on sustainable development in India since the 1991's liberalization policy. The study used

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the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model to test the relationship between sustainable development and trade openness along with other control variables that are supposed to affect sustainable development. The empirical results are contrary to conventionally held beliefs, indicating that trade shares a negative correlation with green GDP growth and a positive correlation with the gap between conventional and green GDP. These findings support the argument that trade openness tends to be both distorting and detrimental to future generations.

Yameogo and Omojolaibi (2021) explored the relationship among trade openness, economic growth, and poverty levels in 40 sub-Saharan African countries from 1990 to 2017. The Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, the Panel Vector Auto-Regression (VAR), and the System of Generalized Method of Moments (SYS-GMM) were employed. A robustness test was also applied and the sensitivity analysis was done through the Panel ARDL model. The results revealed that trade openness, foreign direct investment, and institutional quality significantly increase economic growth in the long-term, while institutional quality reduces economic growth in the short-run. Furthermore, trade liberalization, institutional quality, and population growth rate lead to poverty reduction in the long-run, while trade openness has adverse effects in the short-run. Moreover, poverty does not have a significant response to trade and growth shocks. Poverty presented a positive change, but the level was not significant. The Pairwise Dumitrescu Hurlin Panel Causality results highlighted feedback effects among trade, economic growth, and poverty levels in the region. Based on these findings, the study recommends that governments in Africa should review their poverty reduction programs in order to move towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals.

Unachukwu (2022) investigated the effect of the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme on agricultural sector performance in Anglophone West African countries using annual time series covering a period of 41 years (1980 - 2020). The study used agriculture GDP as the dependent variable and the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme as the main independent variable, whereas agriculture exports, agriculture imports, and exchange rate were used as check variables. The study used all five

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Anglophone ECOWAS countries. The study used descriptive statistics, a correlation matrix, pooled OLS, fixed effect and random effect models, as well as generalized method moment (GMM) modeling techniques for the analysis. The study showed that the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme (ETLSAGL) has a negative effect on agricultural sector performance in Anglophone West African countries - agriculture export to GDP ratio (AGEXAGL) has a negative effect; agriculture import to GDP ratio (AGIMAGL) has a negative effect; exchange rate (EXRCAGL) has a negative effect. The study, therefore, concludes that the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme has not enhanced agricultural sector performance in Anglophone West African countries within the period of study. The study recommends full compliance in the removal of tariff and non-tariff barriers in line with the provisions of ETLs, implementation of the Common External Tariff (CET), and adoption of a common currency by ECOWAS member countries to help mitigate negativity in the exchange rate.

Denwi et al. (2022) used the dynamic growth framework to model the relationship between trade liberalization policy and economic growth in 42 African countries from 1995 to 2018. The study used the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) technique, which is sufficient for inference in a dynamic, heterogeneous environment. The result shows that trade liberalization policy is beneficial to the economic growth of African countries up to a certain threshold, beyond which it begins to cause the economy to under-heat. The paper estimates a threshold value of 139.94% of total trade to GDP, 345.32% of exports to GDP, and 62.80% of imports to GDP. These findings champion the idea that, for countries in Africa to benefit largely from trade, trade openness, export openness, and import openness should hover around the estimated threshold values. The paper documents certain conditions required to moderate the effect of trade liberalization policy on economic growth in African countries.

Empirically, there is a dearth of literature on the relationship between the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme and the economic growth of Anglophone West African countries. Most of the studies reviewed, like Yameogo and Omojolaibi (2021), examined the relationship between trade liberalization, economic growth, and poverty levels in sub-Saharan Africa; Denwi et al. (2022) studied the effect of trade liberalization

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policy on economic growth in Africa; and Asante (2018) assessed the role of the ETLS as a Vehicle for the Promotion of a West African Free Trade Area. Specifically, Unachukwu (2022) studied the effect of the ETLS on agricultural sector performance in Anglophone West African countries. The present study deviates from these scholars by examining the effect of the ECOWAS Trade Liberalization Scheme on economic growth in Anglophone West African countries by using ETLS (as a dummy), total intra export, total intra import, and exchange rate by employing a pooled mean group (PMG) because of the heterogeneity of income and trade policies as well as other socioeconomic and socio-political factors embedded in Africa from 1981 to 2021.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Model Specification

The model specification of this study mimics the work of Unachukwu (2022) with a slight modification. Unachukwu (2022), who studied the effect of the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme on agricultural sector performance in Anglophone West African countries from 1980 to 2020, modeled:

$$\text{AGRPAGL} = f(\text{ETLSAGL}, \text{AGEXAGL}, \text{AGIMAGL}, \text{EXRCAGL}) \quad (3.1)$$

Where;

AGRPAGL = Agricultural sector performance proxied by the proportion of agriculture to GDP

ETLSAGL = ECOWAS liberalization scheme proxied by dummy

AGEXAGL = Agric Export

AGIMAGL = Agric Import

EXRCAGL = Exchange rate

The present study deviates from this study by examining the effect of the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme on economic growth in Anglophone ECOWAS countries by using the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme (ETLS), total intra-regional exports (XPOT), total intra-regional imports (MPOT), and exchange rate (EXRC) as the explanatory variables. Hence, the functional relationship was stated as:

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$$EGRT = f(ETLS, XPOT, MPOT, EXRC) \quad (3.1)$$

Where;

EGRT = Economic growth proxied by GDP growth rate

ETLS = ECOWAS liberalization scheme proxied by dummy

XPOT = Total Export within the region

MPOT = Total Import within the region

EXRC = Exchange rate

The mathematical form of the model or equation(3.1) takes the form of;

$$EGRT = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ETLS + \beta_2 XPOT + \beta_3 MPOT + \beta_4 EXRC \quad (3.2)$$

The linear econometric form of the model or equation(3.3) takes the form of;

$$EGRT = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ETLS + \beta_2 XPOT + \beta_3 MPOT + \beta_4 EXRC + \mu \quad (3.3)$$

Where;

β_0 are the intercepts

β_1 - β_4 are the coefficients of independent variables while μ is the error terms.

EGRT, ETLS, XPOT, MPOT, EXRC are as earlier defined.

3.2 Data Required/Sources

The data for this study are annual time series collected from secondary sources covering a period of 32 years (1981 to 2021). Some of these sources include publications of the World Bank and world development indicators (WDI) as presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Variables Description and Sources of Data

S/N	Variables	Description of Data	Source
1	EGRT	Economic growth proxied by GDP growth rate (%)	World Development Indicator (WDI)
2	ETLS	ECOWAS Trade Liberalisation Scheme proxied by Dummy	Author's Computation
3	XPOT	Total Exports of Goods Intra ECOWAS (Million US dollars)	ECOWAS
4	MPOT	Total Imports of Goods Intra ECOWAS (Million US dollars)	ECOWAS
5	EXRC	Exchange Rate (LCU per US\$)	World Development Indicator (WDI)

Source: Author's Compilation from Economic Literature (2023)

3.3 Estimation Techniques and Procedures

This study adopts descriptive statistics, correlation matrix analysis, and inferential analytical tools. Specifically, it will adopt the panel unit root test, Hausman test, and pooled mean group (PMG) to estimate the effect of the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme on economic growth in Anglophone West African countries.

3.4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics is the type of statistics that involves organizing, summarizing, and presenting data in a meaningful or usable format. Thus, in this research, simple averages (i.e., the mean), histograms, kurtosis, and Jarque-Bera shall be employed to analyze the trends on some of the variables used in this study.

3.4.2 Correlation Matrix

A correlation matrix is simply a table that displays the correlation coefficients for different variables. The matrix depicts the relationship between all the possible pairs of values in a table. It is a powerful tool to summarize a large dataset and to identify and visualize patterns in the given data. A correlation matrix consists of rows and columns that show the variables. Each cell in a table contains the correlation coefficient.

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Dr. Itode J. KRAMA, Dr. Edward WASURUM
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3.6.4 PanelARDL

A panel autoregressive distributed lag model (ARDL) is used to analyze the effect of the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme on economic growth in anglophone ECOWAS countries. This framework helps in determining both the long and short-run impacts of the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme on economic growth. Specifically, the study used the pooled mean group (PMG) for the analysis. The study adopts the PMG estimator because it allows a greater degree of parameter heterogeneity than the usual estimator procedures used in empirical growth studies by imposing common long-run relationships across countries while allowing for heterogeneity in the short-run responses and intercepts. That is, the pooled mean group is an intermediate estimator that allows the short-term parameters to differ between groups while imposing equality of the long-term coefficients between groups.

3.6.5 A priori Expectation

It is expected that increases in these variables—the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme (ETLS), exports (XPOT), imports (MPOT), and exchange rate (EXRC)—will enhance economic growth in Anglophone ECOWAS countries such as Gambia, Ghana, Liberia, Nigeria, and Sierra Leone.

Table 3.1: A priori Expectation

Variables	A priori Expectation
ETLS	Positive (+)
XPOT	Positive (+)
MPOT	Positive (+)
EXRC	Positive (+)

Source: *Researcher's Computation*

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4. Data Analysis and Interpretation

The analysis of the data was done in phases. The first phase is the descriptive statistics to ascertain the behavior of the variables. Second, the analyses of the correlation matrix to see the relationship between the variables. Third, the analyses of the unit root test to determine the order of integration. Fourth, the Hausman test to determine whether to use MG or PMG. Fifth, the long-run and short-run results of the PMG; and lastly, the short run results of each of the countries.

4.2.1 Descriptive statistics for all countries

The descriptive statistics show and explain the characteristics or behavior of each of the variables in the models. The result of the descriptive statistics for all the variables is presented in Table 4.1 below:

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics Test Results

	EGRT	ETLS	LNXPOT	LNMPOT	LNEXRC
Mean	2.93069	0.7804878	7.834797	1.459833	587.3766
Maximum	26.41732	1	46.45172	7.556419	10439.43
Minimum	-30.14513	0	.0059455	.139122	.0002749
Std. Dev.	5.70127	0.4149294	10.81385	1.229742	1677.462
Observations	205	205	205	205	205

Source: *Extract from Stata 13*

The descriptive statistic results for Anglophone West African countries are shown in table 4.1. The table shows that economic growth (EGRT) has a mean value of 2.93069 with a standard deviation of 5.70127. Also, ETLS has a mean value of 0.7804878 with a standard deviation of 0.4149294. Again, total export (XPOT) has a mean value of 7.834797 with a standard deviation of 10.81385, while total import (MPOT) has a mean value of 1.459833 with a standard deviation of 1.229742. Furthermore, Exchange Rate (EXR) has a mean value of 587.3766 with a standard deviation of 1677.462.

4.2.2 Correlation Matrix Results

The correlation matrix shows that the regressors do not have perfect or exact linear representations of one another (that is, to avoid multicollinearity). The result of the correlation matrix for all the variables is presented in Table 4.2. It presents the results for Anglophone ECOWAS countries. This is necessary so as to ensure that the variables used in this study do not show perfect multicollinearity (i.e., variation in one explanatory variable can be completely explained by movements in another explanatory variable), as this will give rise to biased estimates. As shown in the matrix above, the correlation coefficient between a variable and itself is one. The correlation matrix is used to test the data for multicollinearity. This is ruled out as long as the coefficient of correlation between any two explanatory variables is not equal to one or very close to one, that is, 80 and above. The correlation matrix of the variables is presented below:

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix Test Results

	EGRT	ETLS	XPOT	MPOT	EXRC
EGRT	1.0000				
ETLS	0.2001	1.0000			
XPOT	-0.0545	0.1304	1.0000		
MPOT	0.1507	0.0905	-0.3682	1.0000	
EXRC	0.0320	0.4358	-0.1239	0.1033	1.0000

Source: *Extract from Stata 13*

Table 4.2 shows that none of the variables were perfectly correlated with each other, which is equal to one or very close to one, suggesting that there is no multicollinearity in the model. This is because none of the paired variables has a correlation coefficient of one or more than 80 percent and above. Also, the table shows that except for XPOT, the other variables such as ETLS, MPOT, and EXR have a positive correlation with EGRT.

4.2.3 Panel Unit Root Test

Table 4.3 presents the results of the panel unit root test for stationarity test for each of the variables used in this study using the Im, Pesaran, and Shin (IPS) and Levin-Lin-Chu unit-root tests.

Table 4.3: Im-Pesaran-Shin (IPS) Unit Root Test Results

Variables	ADF at Level	P-Value	ADF at 1 st Difference	P-Value	Status	Remarks
EGRT	-1.2358	0.1083	-7.1209	0.0000	I(1)	Stationary
ETLS	-1.0937	0.1370	-7.0273	0.0000	I(1)	Stationary
LNXPOT	-1.9941	0.0231	-	-	I(0)	Stationary
LNMPOT	-3.5565	0.0002	-	-	I(0)	Stationary
LNEXRC	-1.3324	0.0914	-2.3880	0.0085	I(1)	Stationary

Levin-Lin-Chu (LLC) Unit Root Test Results						
Variables	ADF at Level	P-Value	ADF at 1 st Difference	P-Value	Status	Remarks
EGRT	-0.8050	0.2104	-6.9989	0.0000	I(1)	Stationary
ETLS	-2.6123	0.0045	-	-	I(0)	Stationary
LNXPOT	-1.2257	0.1102	-6.8207	0.0000	I(1)	Stationary
LNMPOT	-9.2642	0.0000	-	-	I(0)	Stationary
LNEXRC	-6.1757	0.0000	-	-	I(0)	Stationary

Source: Extract from Stata 13

The results of the panel unit root test in table 4.3 reveal that XPOT and MPOT were stationary at level while EGRT, ETLS, and EXRC were stationary at the first difference under the Im-Pesaran-Shin unit-root test. ETLS, MPOT, and EXRC were stationary at level while EGRT and XPOT were stationary at the first difference under the Levin-Lin-Chu unit-root test. The result depicts that the independent variables used in the model were integrated of both order zero and one, that is, I(1) and I(0), and the dependent

variable was integrated of order one, that is, $I(1)$. Since the results indicate that the series are of mixed order of integration, the appropriate test to use in this study is the panel ARDL (pooled mean group) test. According to Giles (1975), Perasan, Shin, and Smith (2001), Jawaid and Waheed (2016), and Salisu (2016), when the series used in any study are of different order of integration, the appropriate test to use is the panel ARDL test.

4.2.3 Hausman Test Results for MG and PMG

Table 4.4 presents the Hausman test results for MG and PMG. This will enable the researcher to determine whether to use the mean group (MG) or the pooled mean group (PMG).

Table 4.4: Hausman Test Result

Variables	Coefficients			Standard Error	Prob
	(b)- mg	(B)- pmg	$\sqrt{\text{diag}(V_b - V_B)}$. Difference		
Etls	-4.570027	-1.143283	-3.426744	2.067073	Prob>chi2 = 0.5689
Lnspot	60.56661	-.1697266	60.73634	67.94393	
Lnmpot	-18.41278	.9036746	-19.31646	23.56817	
Lnexrc	-1.153739	.8596189	-2.013358	2.887302	

Source: Extract from Stata 13

From Table 4.4, the result of the Hausman test reveals that the Prob value is 0.5689, which is greater than the 5 percent level. Since the Prob value is 0.5689 (i.e., 57 percent), the null hypothesis of homogeneity cannot be rejected. Hence, the model supports the pooled mean group (PMG) estimator as adopted by the researcher.

4.2.3 PARDL Long Run and Short Run Results for All Selected Countries

Table 4.5 presents the long and short-run results of the panel ARDL for the model across all specifications using the pooled mean group (PMG). This will enable the researcher to find out the long-run effect of ETLS on economic growth in Anglophone ECOWAS countries.

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Dr. Itode J. KRAMA, Dr. Edward WASURUM

and Dr. Bright K. ABORH

Table 4.5: PMG Long and Short Run Result for all the Countries

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z-Statistic	Prob-Value
Long Run				
ETLS	-1.14328	1.25459	-0.910	0.362
LNXPOT	-0.16973	0.32178	-0.530	0.598
LNMPOT	0.90367	0.86238	1.050	0.295
LNEXRC	0.85962	0.30406	2.830	0.005
Short Run				
ECT	-0.85342	0.12542	-6.800	0.000
ETLS (-1)	2.91272	1.86885	1.560	0.119
LNXPOT (-1)	2.07797	3.23699	0.64	0.521
LNMPOT (-1)	-1.80169	1.00199	-1.800	0.072
LNEXRC (-1)	1.17275	1.45984	0.800	0.422
C	0.55355	1.07818	0.510	0.608

Source: *Extract from Stata 13*

From Table 4.5, the long-run result of the analysis across all specifications reveals that the coefficients of the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme (ETLS) and total intra export (XPOT) have a negative and insignificant relationship with economic growth; total intra import (MPOT) has a positive and insignificant relationship with economic growth; and the exchange rate (EXRC) has a positive and significant relationship with economic growth in the long-run.

From the short-run model, the error correction term of -0.85342 with a prob-value of 0.000 shows that there is a cointegration among the variables in the model. Hence, there is long-run cointegration at a 5 percent level. So, any deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected at about 85 percent adjustment speed. Also, the study reveals that across all specifications of the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme (ETLS), total intra export (XPOT) and exchange rate (EXRC) have a positive and insignificant relationship with economic growth, while total intra import (MPOT) has a negative and

insignificant relationship with economic growth in the short-run.

4.2.4 Short-Run Results for Gambia

Table 4.6 presents the short-run estimation results of the model for Gambia. This will enable the researcher to find out the short-run effect of ETLs on economic growth in the country.

Table 4.6: PMG Short-Run Result for Gambia

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z-Statistic	Prob-Value
ECT	-1.12854	0.16014	-7.050	0.000
ETLS (-1)	1.80917	3.46665	0.520	0.602
LNXPOT (-1)	-0.47423	0.36235	-1.310	0.191
LNMPOT (-1)	1.52468	1.86398	0.820	0.413
LNEXRC (-1)	3.15187	4.43255	0.710	0.477
C	1.75873	1.16231	1.510	0.130

Source: *Extract from Stata 13*

The short-run analysis reveals that, in Gambia, the error correction coefficient (ECC) is statistically significant and appropriately signed. Since the error correction term is -1.12854 with a prob-value of 0.000, it shows that there is a cointegration among the variables in the model in Gambia. Hence, there is long-run cointegration at a 5 percent level. And any deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected at about 113 percent adjustment speed.

Also, the study found that ETLs, MPOT, and EXRC have a positive and insignificant relationship with economic growth in Gambia, while XPOT has a negative and insignificant relationship with economic growth in the country within the period under review.

4.2.4 Short Run Results for Ghana

Table 4.7 presents the short-run estimation results of the model for Ghana. This will enable the researcher to find out the short-run effect of ETLs on economic growth in the country.

Table 4.7: PMG Short-Run Result for Ghana

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z-Statistic	Prob-Value
ECT	-0.57160	0.14098	-4.050	0.000
ETLS (-1)	-0.59561	2.69048	-0.220	0.825
LNXPOT (-1)	0.48352	0.98803	0.490	0.625
LNMPOT (-1)	-1.98963	1.37593	-1.450	0.148
LNEXRC (-1)	2.72177	1.64514	1.650	0.098
C	3.39411	1.34172	2.530	0.011

Source: *Extract from Stata 13*

The short-run analysis reveals that, in Ghana, the error correction coefficient (ECC) is statistically significant and appropriately signed. Since the error correction term is -0.57160 with a prob-value of 0.000, it shows that there is a cointegration among the variables in the model in Ghana. Hence, there is a long-run cointegration at a 5 percent level; and any deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected at about 57 percent adjustment speed.

Also, the study found that, within the period under review, ETLS and MPOT had a negative and insignificant relationship with economic growth in Ghana, while XPOT and EXRC had a positive and insignificant relationship with economic growth.

4.2.4 Short-Run Results for Liberia

Table 4.8 presents the short-run estimation results of the model for Liberia. This will enable the researcher to find out the short-run effect of customs and excise duties on the manufacturing sector's performance in Liberia.

Table 4.9: PMG Short-Run Result for Nigeria

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z-Statistic	Prob-Value
ECT	-0.59599	0.10823	-5.510	0.000
ETLS (-1)	9.57230	3.32174	2.880	0.004
LNXPOT (-1)	0.79162	0.41693	1.900	0.058
LNMPOT (-1)	-0.92414	0.95322	-0.970	0.332
LNEXRC (-1)	-2.79216	1.86951	-1.490	0.135
C	0.91573	0.89085	1.030	0.304

Source: *Extract from Stata 13*

The short-run analysis reveals that, in Nigeria, the error correction coefficient (ECC) is statistically significant and appropriately signed. Since the error correction term is -0.59599 with a prob-value of 0.000, it shows that there is a cointegration among the variables in the model in Nigeria. Hence, there is long-run cointegration at a 5 percent level; and any deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected at about 60 percent adjustment speed.

Also, the study found that, within the period under review, ETLS has a positive and significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria; XPOT has a positive but insignificant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria while MPOT and EXRC have a negative but insignificant relationship with economic growth.

4.2.4 Short-Run Results for Sierra Leone

Table 4.10 presents the short-run estimation results of the model for Sierra Leone. This will enable the researcher to find out the short-run effect of customs and excise duties on the manufacturing sector's performance in Sierra Leone.

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Dr. Itode J. KRAMA, Dr. Edward WASURUM
and Dr. Bright K. ABORH

Table 4.8: PMG Short-Run Result for Liberia

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z-Statistic	Prob-Value
ECT	-0.81471	0.16125	-5.050	0.000
ETLS (-1)	-0.33364	6.07285	-0.050	0.956
LNXPOT (-1)	14.3885	37.7496	0.380	0.703
LNMPOT (-1)	-3.53997	10.5127	-0.340	0.736
LNEXRC (-1)	4.59191	11.4212	0.400	0.688
C	-0.25714	1.63590	-0.160	0.875

Source: *Extract from Stata 13*

The short-run analysis reveals that in Liberia, the error correction coefficient (ECC) is statistically significant and appropriately signed. Since the error correction term is -0.81471, with a prob-value of 0.000, it shows that there is a cointegration among the variables in the model in Liberia. Hence, there is long-run cointegration at a 5 percent level. Hence, any deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected at about 81% adjustment speed.

Also, the study found that ETLS and MPOT have a negative and an insignificant relationship with economic growth in Liberia, while XPOT and EXRC have a positive and an insignificant relationship with economic growth within the period under review.

4.2.4 Short-Run Results for Nigeria

Table 4.9 presents the short-run estimation results of the model for Nigeria. This will enable the researcher to find out the short-run effect of customs and excise duties on the manufacturing sector's performance in Nigeria.

Table 4.10: PMG Short-Run Result for Sierra Leone

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z-Statistic	Prob-Value
ECT	-1.15624	0.16578	-6.970	0.000
ETLS (-1)	4.11137	7.82486	0.530	0.599
LNXPOT (-1)	-4.79961	1.48778	-3.230	0.001
LNMPOT (-1)	-4.07941	3.59987	-1.130	0.257
LNEXRC (-1)	-1.80965	4.65641	-0.390	0.698
C	-3.04367	2.75616	-1.100	0.269

Source: *Extract from Stata 13*

The short-run analysis reveals that, in Sierra Leone, the error correction coefficient (ECC) is statistically significant and appropriately signed. Since the error correction term is -1.15624 with a prob-value of 0.000, it shows that there is a cointegration among the variables in the model in Sierra Leone. Hence, there is long-run cointegration at a 5 percent level; and any deviations from the long-run equilibrium are corrected at about 116% adjustment speed.

Also, the study found that, within the period under review, ETLS has a positive and insignificant relationship with economic growth in Sierra Leone; XPOT has a negative and a significant relationship with economic growth in Sierra Leone, while MPOT and EXRC have a negative and insignificant relationship.

4. Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

The study investigated empirically the effect of the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme on economic growth in Anglophone West African countries using annual time series covering a period of 41 years (1981 – 20210). The study used GDP growth rate as the dependent variable to proxy economic growth and used the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme as the main independent variable, whereas total intra exports (XPOT), total intra imports (MPOT), and exchange rate (EXRC) were used as check variables. The study used all five Anglophone ECOWAS countries for the analysis. The study used descriptive statistics, a correlation matrix, the panel unit root test, the Hausman test for MG and PMG, as well as pooled mean group (PMG) modeling techniques for the analysis. The study shows that, in the long-run across all

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specifications, the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme (ETLS) has a negative and insignificant relationship with economic growth, while in the short-run across all specifications, it has a positive and insignificant relationship with economic growth. In Gambia, ETLS has both positive and negative insignificant relationships with economic growth; it has a negative and insignificant relationship with economic growth in Liberia; it has a positive and a significant relationship with economic growth in Nigeria; and also has a positive and insignificant relationship with economic growth in Sierra Leone.

Predicated on the above, the study concludes that the ECOWAS trade liberalization scheme has not improved economic growth in Anglophone West African countries within the period of study. The insignificant relationship between ETLS and economic growth in Anglophone West African countries may be in line with what Fajana (2018) observed that lack of political will on the part of member states to surrender part of their sovereignty to implement the ETLS; the great disconnect between adoption of policies at the regional level and implementation at the national level; lack of trust on the part of some member states in the transparency of the process of determining product eligibility and issuing of certificate of origin under the ETLS; absence of an effective mechanism for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of the ETLS and of a legal framework for settlement of disputes and enforcement of rights and obligations; and capacity deficiencies (both institutional and technical) of the ECOWAS Commission, among others, are some of the challenges and constraints in the implementation of the ETLS in West Africa. The study therefore recommends that ECOWAS member countries fully implement the removal of tariff and non-tariff barriers in accordance with ETLS regulations and adopt a common currency within the region.

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